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Lymphocyte apoptosis for prediction of individual normal tissue radiosensitivity in cancer patients treated with radiotherapy

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Radiation-induced lymphocyte apoptosis assay based on flow cytometry is one of the most promising functional radiosensitivity assays for predicting the individual normal tissue reactions to radiotherapy in cancer patients. Preclinical and multicenter clinical studies demonstrated that the apoptosis levels of CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ T lymphocytes caused by ex vivo irradiation of patients' blood samples before radiotherapy have been related to the severity of late radiotherapy side effects in cancer patients. The higher level of radiation-induced apoptosis of patient-derived lymphocytes has been associated with a lower risk of developing a higher grade of late radiation-induced normal tissue radiotoxicity. The determination of radiation-induced apoptosis level of CD8⁺ T lymphocytes was shown to be more sensitive and specific test than the level of CD4⁺ T lymphocytes. In addition, a subpopulation of CD4⁺ T lymphocytes was reported to be more resistant to radiation than CD8⁺ T lymphocytes. The possible clinical value of assessment of lymphocyte apoptosis rate caused by irradiation for the prediction of risk for developing radiation-induced toxicity has been demonstrated in patients with different types of malignant tumors: breast cancer, prostate cancer, lung cancer, cervical cancer, radiation-induced sarcoma, and head and neck cancer. The different lymphocyte apoptosis scores were found in various cancer types, suggesting the need for establishing threshold values for each cancer type. The level of evidence I of this predictive assay implicates its adoption in routine clinical practice in the near future.

Examination of the response of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T lymphocytes to irradiation at the level of genome, transcriptome, epigenome, and proteome for each cancer type is crucial to shed light on molecular mechanisms underlying radiotoxicity and differences in apoptosis scores, and also to

reveal novel biomarkers associated with individual normal tissue radiosensitivity for personalized treatment approaches. The integration of levels of radiation-induced lymphocyte apoptosis and individual, clinical, and treatment-related factors, and molecular biomarkers into robust machine learning-based models for predicting radiotoxicity is a promising approach for the development of personalized radiotherapy, improvement of the outcome and patients' life quality.

Keywords: radiotherapy, cancer patients, individual radiosensitivity, lymphocyte apoptosis

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